

Retention of aldrin in soil

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Soil-inhabiting gryllids *Brachytrypes portentosus* and *Gryllotalpa africana* frequently pose a problem to direct-seeded upland rice in northern West Bengal. The infestation is generally prevented by the application of 5% aldrin dust. Aldrin, one of the most persistent cyclodiene insecticides, is being phased out, however.

Aldrin disappears from European and American soils in approximately 3 years on the average. In terai soils of Jalpaiguri district in North Bengal, its bioactivity rapidly wanes and insect reinfestation occurs within about 5 months after application. An experiment on the retention of aldrin in sandy loam and alluvial soils was therefore conducted.

To study the soil retention of aldrin a copper cylinder 23.1 cm high and 7 cm in diameter with 1 outlet through a short spout in the bottom was used. Filter paper was wrapped around a perforated

Residue of aldrin in 2 different soils (mean of 3 samples) of Jalpaiguri district, northernwest Bengal, India.

Soil type	Aldrin recovered (ppm) when leached with				Control (ppm)
	153.24 mm water	229.86 mm water	510.80 mm water	1532.40 mm water	
Terai (sandy loam)	26	22	12	5	36
Alluvium (silty loam)	22	16	2	1	35

copper disc that just fitted the bottom of the cylinder. Two grams of fresh 5% aldrin dust of 75 µm particle size was thoroughly mixed with 2.4 kg of each air-dried soil type. Then 800 g samples were placed in copper cylinders and lightly compacted, making the soil column 14.22 cm high. The cylinders were then clamped to a stand.

Next 97.8 ml distilled water was percolated through the soil columns in installments. Soil in a control cylinder received no water. After the experiments, the soils were collected from the cylinders, air-dried, and analyzed for residue by gas liquid chromatography at the Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi. The results are in the table.

Aldrin is substantially displaced or inactivated in both soil types. The

reduction, however, is most appreciable in the sandy loam soil, which contains more organic matter (mostly undecomposed). Possibly because of rapid aldrin reduction, reinfestation by soil insects occurs.

Invitation to authors

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two paragraphs and a table, figure, or photograph. They are subject to editing and abridgement to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.

Pest management and control

WEEDS

Weed management studies on direct-seeded and transplanted rice in 1976 aus in Bangladesh

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A study was begun in 1976 to compare the effectiveness of herbicides with that of hand weeding to identify weed differences between plots of short-statured and of taller local varieties and to determine the weed-caused yield reduction in direct-seeded and transplanted rice.

BR3 – a short-statured, high yielding rice variety – and Dhariāl – a tall local variety – were direct-seeded in rows into dry soil 13 April. Thirty-day-old seedlings

Yield of BR3 and Dhariāl rice under various weed management practices in the 1976 aus season, Dacca, Bangladesh.

Treatment	Herbicide rate ^a (kg a.i./ha)	Yield ^b (t/ha)					
		Direct seeded			Transplanted		
		BR3	Dhariāl	Mean	BR3	Dhariāl	Mean
Butachlor							
+ hand weeding	0.5	5.99	3.04	4.52 a	6.68	1.49	4.09 a
Hand weeding	–	5.69	2.45	4.01 ab	6.43	1.45	3.94 ab
Butachlor	1.5	4.11	2.05	3.38 b	6.09	1.39	3.14 b
Thiobencarb	1.5	4.44	2.49	3.46 b	5.99	1.39	3.69 b
Piperophos/ dimethametryn	1.2/0.3	4.12	1.91	3.55 b	5.91	1.36	3.66 b
Control	–	3.25	1.32	2.30 c	5.95	1.36	3.66 b
Av.		4.80 b	2.22 c	3.52	6.19 a	1.41 d	3.79

^a Applied 3 days after seeding.

^b Any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

were transplanted 4 May in rows 20 × 20 cm apart. Herbicides for six weed control treatments (see table) were

applied 3 days after seeding and were activated by irrigating the plots. The recommended levels of cultural practices